

From theory to practice: A motion capture project (methodology) as a platform for active and problem-based learning

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Abstract

A major challenge in engineering education is the effective transition from theoretical knowledge to its application in real-world environments. In this context, participation in consolidated technology projects provides students with the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts in practical scenarios, thereby enhancing their understanding and problem-solving skills. The following article presents the experience of a group of students who participated in a motion capture project based on inertial sensors. The initiative was structured in three phases: validation of the data obtained from the sensors, evaluation of the repeatability of the measurements, and development of a user interface for visualization and analysis of the information. The objective of this project focused on two factors: first, to explore alternatives for motion capture using opto-reflective cameras, and second, to determine the feasibility of performing these tests in the open field. The methodological approach adopted reflects the phases of an engineering development cycle: from conceptualization and system design, through implementation of data acquisition hardware and software, to experimental testing in two scenarios: UR5 collaborative robots and human applications. Finally, this experience demonstrates how the integration of technology projects in engineering can enhance active and problem-based learning strategies. By encouraging multidisciplinary work and direct application of knowledge to real-world situations, it facilitates students' transition from a theoretical approach to an applied, problem-based understanding of engineering.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Problem-Based Learning; Motion Capture.

1 Introduction

The preparation of engineering students for professional practice necessitates a multifaceted approach that extends beyond theoretical knowledge and mathematical foundations. While a robust understanding of these principles is imperative, it is equally crucial to furnish students with opportunities to apply their learning to authentic challenges in the real world. Conventional engineering curricula frequently accord theoretical concepts a higher level of importance than practical applications. This imbalance in curricular emphasis can result in graduate students lacking the necessary skills and experience to effectively navigate the multifaceted challenges inherent in their chosen field (Parkinson et al., 2022).

To address this discrepancy, contemporary engineering education is undergoing a transformation to incorporate projects that consider social, economic, and cultural contexts (Banday et al., 2014), as well as collaborative initiatives between students at various academic levels and partnerships with industry (Tubbs et al., 2024). Despite these advancements, challenges persist in the effective integration of real-world problem-solving into the curriculum and in the development of crucial non-technical skills such as teamwork and communication (Male et al., 2010; Soupeze, 2023).

Active learning methodologies, including problem-based learning (PBL), scenario-based learning (SBL), and inquiry-based learning (IBL), have been identified as promising strategies for addressing these challenges. These approaches facilitate the application of theory, provide access to diverse resources, and foster collaborative learning environments (Marnewick, 2023). PBL, for instance, employs complex, real-world

problems as the primary context for acquiring knowledge and developing critical skills, encouraging inquiry, collaboration, and effective communication (Anchunda & Kaewurai, 2025). SBL and IBL further enhance learning by immersing students in realistic scenarios and promoting exploratory investigation (Nicholus et al., 2023).

A project that focuses on biomechanical applications is one such initiative that aims to address these educational needs. Biomechanics, defined as the study of the mechanics of living organisms (Hamill et al., 2015), is a field that has benefited from the development of tools such as motion capture systems. These systems have enabled the quantification of movement and the provision of objective data for clinical assessments. These systems, which employ technologies ranging from cameras to inertial measurement units (IMUs), present an alternative to subjective evaluations (Gómez Echeverry et al., 2018).

While optoelectronic systems are widely regarded as the gold standard for motion capture, their cost and specialized requirements can impose limitations on accessibility (Cunningham & Brooks, 2022; Romero-Flores et al., 2024). In contrast, IMUs are more portable and affordable, making them suitable for undergraduate projects. However, their accuracy is still under investigation (Taheri et al., 2020). To promote accessible motion capture research, Tecnológico de Monterrey established the SAM research group, which focuses on developing a whole-body motion capture system using IMUs, such as the BNO080 sensor. The goal is to create an accurate, real-time, 3D orientation system using readily available components.

2 Methodology

The methodological design of this project was intentionally structured to exemplify and integrate distinct active learning strategies within engineering education. Each phase of the project corresponded to a specific pedagogical approach: the initial phase was grounded in PBL, the second phase was aligned with SBL, and the final phase incorporated elements of IBL. This alignment was intended to foster the development of both technical and non-technical competencies among participants, including critical thinking, adaptability, and user-centered design.

The SAM research group, established through a collaboration between academic and research entities, is oriented around three principal domains: system design, technological development, and functional performance evaluation. The latter domain constituted the primary focus of the present study.

The methodology employed in this project is thoroughly delineated in the thesis (Amorocho & Perea Calderon, 2022), and it is composed of three sequential phases, each designed to evaluate a different aspect of system performance and student learning. The first phase involved validation in a controlled environment, the second phase extended the evaluation to real-world scenarios, and the third phase addressed the development of a user interface tailored to the needs of end-users.

2.1 Controlled evaluation

In this phase, students had the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a controlled setting, using the UR5e robot to validate the accuracy of the SAM sensors. This facilitated a direct comparison of sensor data with a gold-standard optoelectronic system (VICON), thereby promoting critical thinking and problem-solving as the researchers analyzed discrepancies and refined their measurement techniques.

For this stage, the UR5e robot was used, which consists of a programmable mechanical arm that allows to control the range of movement and the speed SAM sensors were placed on specific robot segments (see Figure 1), as well as the location of markers on the robotic arm to record it with VICON.

Figure 1. (a) Location of sensors on the robotic arm Ure5. (b) Location of the VICON markers on the robotic arm (represented by the yellow dots)

With this, the UR5e was programmed for three flexion-extension movements (vertical, horizontal and two-link) at five speeds ($5^\circ/s, 120^\circ/s, 150^\circ/s, 180^\circ/s$), as shown in Figure 22, at the beginning of each test, the robot performed a synchronization event, which simulated a football kick.

Figure 2. Movement Routine for data validation: (a) Horizontal flexion-extension (b) Vertical flexion-extension (c) Flexion extension 2 links.

All movements were captured simultaneously with the optoelectronic motion capture system Vicon and the SAM sensors. The captured data was pre-processed using NEXUS (software provided by VICON for the acquisition of marker data) and MATLAB, in order to perform a cross-correlation between SAM and VICON data. In this way, the data was compared using the Bland-Altman statistical test, Pearson's correlation and the root mean square error (RMSE) value.

2.2 Evaluation in a real scenario

In this phase, students engaged in Scenario-Based Learning by applying their knowledge to real-world contexts. The subjects were responsible for the installation of the sensors and for serving as test subjects. This required them to adapt to the variability and unpredictability of human movement. This phase placed significant emphasis on teamwork, communication, and the capacity for problem-solving in a less structured environment. During this phase, students had the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a controlled setting, utilizing the UR5e robot to validate the accuracy of the SAM sensors. This facilitated a direct comparison of sensor data with a gold-standard optoelectronic system (VICON), thereby promoting critical thinking and problem-solving as the researchers analyzed discrepancies and refined their measurement techniques.

Figure 3. (a) Location of sensors on subjects. (b) Location of the VICON markers on subjects.

For the purposes of the repeatability tests, a set of SAM sensors was installed on the subjects (Figure 3), as well as the location of the VICON markers (see Figure 3), and a two-day test was performed. The participants in the project rotated as researchers to install the sensors and perform the test and rotated as subjects, this test for the information endorsed by a medical service, with informed consent. It consisted of two phases: The first was stretching (Figure 24), in which the participant was asked to maintain a position for a period. The second consisted of four sequences of four repetitions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Repeatability test routine.

The collected data underwent processing and transformation into the articular angles of the lower extremity (hip, knee, and ankle). This transformation enabled the determination of flexion-extension, abduction-adduction, and rotation in each of the joints. The difference in measurements for each segment between days and researchers on the same subject was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE) value, the Bland-Altman method, and Pearson's correlation.

2.3 User interface approach

In this phase, students engaged in Inquiry-Based Learning by identifying the needs of end-users (healthcare professionals) and designing a user interface that would facilitate the practical application of the motion capture system. This required them to gather feedback, pose questions about usability, and iteratively improve their design based on real-world requirements.

When designing the interface, data that might be of interest to healthcare professionals. Is considered It was important to consider the different stages of data collection, such as patient information, sensor position, and factors associated with patient diagnoses.

3 Results and discussion

In order to comprehend the outcomes of the motion capture project, it is necessary to consider the learning gains, technical results, and challenges encountered by students as they progressed through each project

phase. Rather than reiterating the methodology, this section highlights the key findings and educational impacts associated with each stage.

3.1 Controlled evaluation

The initial phase, conducted in a controlled environment, yielded strong technical validation of the SAM sensor system. Statistical analysis demonstrated a high degree of agreement between the SAM sensors and the VICON reference system, with Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.99 and root mean square errors (RMSE) of 3.41° (lateral) and 3.95° (frontal). These results confirm the feasibility of using low-cost inertial sensors for motion capture in educational and research contexts.

Figure 5. Example of SAM sensor data from phase 1, (a) unsynchronized data b) synchronized data.

Importantly, this phase also fostered significant learning outcomes. Students engaged in the design and execution of a validation protocol, requiring them to apply theoretical knowledge to practical challenges. The process of calibrating sensors, synchronizing data, and interpreting statistical results promoted critical thinking and iterative problem-solving. These experiences are essential for bridging the gap between theoretical instruction and engineering practice.

Figure 6. Example of angle determination.

Table 3. SAM vs VICON comparison.

		Lateral	Frontal
RMSE		3.41	3.95
Pearson Correlation		0.99	0.99
Bland-Altman Test	Coefficient of Reproducibility	4.96°	5.30°
	Coefficient of Variation	10%	12.4%

3.2 Evaluation in a real scenario

In the subsequent real-world scenario phase, students applied the SAM system to human subjects, encountering increased variability and complexity. Repeatability tests across lower limb joints revealed moderate correlations and higher RMSE values (e.g., hip flexion-extension RMSE: 9.4°, knee flexion-extension RMSE: 16.6°), reflecting the inherent challenges of human movement analysis and sensor placement consistency. flexion-extension, and rotation with the results summarized in Table 9. Average result of repeatability tests. Table 9. This approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the repeatability and accuracy of the SAM system in capturing human motion.

Figure 7. Graphic display example: (a) Ankle angles charts. (b) knee angles charts. (c) Hip angles charts.

Table 4. Average result of repeatability tests.

		r	RMSE	RPC(°)
Hip	Flex ext	0.364	9.417	36.617
	Abd Abb	0.302	14.691	42.944
	Rot	0.296	13.936	50.283
Knee	Flex ext	0.239	16.617	51.072
	Abd Abb	0.351	10.128	60.817
	Rot	0.262	13.067	40.700
Ankle	Flex ext	0.294	16.283	49.278
	Abd Abb	0.227	7.906	23.100
	Rot	0.189	11.106	31.411

This phase was instrumental in the development of non-technical skills. The students alternated between the roles of experimenter and subject, a process which demanded effective teamwork, communication and

adaptability. The necessity to standardize procedures and address unanticipated issues in real time engendered an authentic experience in collaborative problem-solving and project management.

3.3 User interface approach

The user interface, developed in the final phase, was evaluated based on usability and end-user feedback rather than technical implementation details. The interface was designed to facilitate streamlined data entry, sensor mapping, and automated report generation. Feedback from healthcare professionals highlighted the value of customisable data displays and integrated reporting features, emphasising the significance of user-centred design.

The iterative development process necessitated that students gather requirements, test prototypes, and refine the interface based on usability observations. This approach served to reinforce inquiry-based learning and adaptability, two key competencies that are integral to the realm of engineering education.

Figure 8. Example of interface implementation (a) Data collection (b) Sensor location (c) Table display (d) PDF document creation.

3.4 Future work

As the project progressed, it became evident that the students exhibited a diverse range of work trajectories, contingent on their specializations and the utilization of tools for various pathologies and domains of practice, including Alzheimer's disease and sports. Future work will focus on expanding the application of the SAM system to a broader range of clinical and research scenarios. For example, the system can be adapted to assess gait abnormalities in patients with neurological conditions such as Parkinson's disease or stroke, monitor rehabilitation progress in orthopedic patients, or evaluate movement patterns in athletes for injury prevention. Additionally, the system's flexibility allows for its use in the early detection of degenerative diseases like Alzheimer's, where subtle changes in movement may serve as early indicators. Its application in the domain of ergonomics evaluation within industrial settings is also noteworthy. By tailoring the system to address the specific needs of different pathologies, the project aims to contribute to more personalized and effective healthcare interventions.

Furthermore, the possibility exists for the establishment of analogous objectives through the utilization of disparate tools, such as cameras in lieu of sensors. This observation underscores the capacity of the application of existing projects to catalyze the conception of novel ones by students (Yu, 2024). This underscores the

importance of integrating experiential learning methodologies into education, fostering critical thinking skills, and broadening students' skill sets to meet the demands and scenarios encountered in the real world.

4 Conclusion

The project yielded concrete evidence of the development of critical thinking, teamwork and communication skills. The students demonstrated critical thinking through the process of troubleshooting and data analysis, teamwork through the coordination of experimental protocols, and communication through the presentation of findings to a variety of audiences. These outcomes align with the objectives of active and problem-based learning, supporting their integration into engineering curricula.

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